

SELF- EFFICACY AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE: A STUDY OF HANDBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract: The present study aims to the study was to explore the self-efficacy and social intelligence of handball players in Al-Qadisiyah, Iraq. The samples of the study consisted of 60 handball players from clubs in Al-Qadisiyah Governorate, Iraq, from the male category only. The basic theory of self-efficacy according to (Bandura, 1997) is people's belief in their abilities that have a tangible and effective effect. Self-efficacy plays a major role in psychological problems, mental and physical health, and has an impact on countering behaviors and finding solutions. It was measured by Iman Sahrian, Muhammad and Smaghawi 2015, and it consisted of 22 items. Social intelligence means an individual's special box in which information about the world is placed (N. Cantor and J. Kihlstrom, 1987) and according to a five-item Likert scale and a 21-item Likert scale. The data were collected and analyzed statistically using the statistical method SPSS. The arithmetic mean of the sample (N = 60) in the self-efficacy variable was (68.75) and the standard deviation was (10,099). And the arithmetic mean of the sample in the social intelligence variable (N = 60) was (10363) and the standard deviation was (3.060). The correlation between the two variables was (0.891).

Keywords: Self-efficacy, Social intelligence, Handball ,Sports.

I. INTRODUCTION

Players are an essential and important part of competitive sports because they influence the behavior of matches. Taking up playing in clubs is considered one of the difficult and arduous tasks in sports because of focus, accuracy of reaction, good cooperation and physical fitness with other players are among the difficult tasks to fulfill the duties required of the players (McMahon et al. 2007). Regardless of performance they perform, external and environmental conditions such as the atmosphere of matches and the negative responses of some spectators may affect the sporting and behavioral performance of the players. Other side psychological factors such as attention focus, emotional control, and self-confidence may play an important role in decision-making (Weinberg and Richardson, 1990). Through the studies of researchers, they have concluded that the sense of belonging to the community is very important in order to reduce the rates of dropout and retention of judgments (Kellett Warner, 2011). A study conducted in 2014 indicates that referees who do not have enough experience are more exposed to fatigue than referees who have experience, and this also applies to players who have practice (Al-Haliq, M., Altahayneh, Z., and Oudat, M.2014). As this phenomenon is common among some referee. Those who have news and it is called emotional exhaustion. More positive emotions about self-efficacy may assistance players enhance their confidence (Nazarudin et al. 2014). Where an athlete's self-efficacy is defined as the ability to accomplish tasks directed to the athlete. There are studies on sports self-efficacy that states that there is negative correlation between sports performance and low self-efficacy (Hani & Long, 1995; Stajkovic and Luthan, 1998). This

may lead to more errors and increased fatigue as well as a slower reaction (Gilin and Feltz, 2011). Motivational Self-efficacy focus theories largely About the concept of intrinsic motivation and the need for self-determination (Reeve et al., 1986). Lewis has analyzed self-efficacy with a model that predicts physical activity behavior and has found a strong predictor and has also appeared in the presence of positive effects at a high rate of physical activity (Lewis et al., 2016). The enjoyment of sports activities is highly dependent on the task assigned to the athlete and the type of activity such as recreational activity (Helsen et al. 1998). Social experience is directly related to the development of sensation and these are two key factors in overcoming the stress of playing (Kellett& Shilbury. 2007) that social connections between others will help the athlete in the process of making important decisions in matches (Kellett and Shelbury, 2007). This is called group activity. Small social groups are units of information processing and make extensive use of problem solving, innovation, and decision-making processes (Devine et al., 1999). The integrative framework of these systems conversing those differences This is a form of human technology and hence scientific problems can be solved (Hinsz, 2015). Therefore, the sports team may Need good interpersonal skills for succeed in sports tasks. Recent studies have supported social Intelligence, which Describes the group's methodology ability to perform Diversity of the set of cognitive tasks (Engel et al. 2014, 2015). The aim of the current study is to know the Self-efficacy and social Intelligence of handball players on a sample of (N= 60) handball players in AL-Qadisiya, Iraq. The main hypothesis is that there are common aspects between Self-efficacy and social intelligence in handball players.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, the researcher has used questionnaire to collect data for the study. The participants were handball players from different clubs in AL-Qadisiya, Iraq. They were 60 males only. They filled out the questionnaires in an in- presence. Their age ranged from 18 to 24 year.

A. Study variables:

1- The concept of Self-efficacy indicates a person's ability and belief in his or her ability to execute behaviors the essential to produce specific performance accomplishments, as stated by psychologist Albert Bandura says that a strong, good sense of self-efficacy promotes personal well-being and human achievement. A highly self-sufficient person views challenges as things to master and these people recover and resist failure and are likely to attribute failure to a lack of effort as they can control many situations as they have been linked to lower levels of stress (Bandura and Albert. 2010)

2- (N. Cantor and J. Kihlstrom, 1987) defines social intelligence as a box of the individual that stores the information and knowledge around him. Social intelligence is also defined as a measure of the sum of social and self-awareness, the sum of social attitudes and beliefs, and the ability to change social beliefs, and this is what distinguishes us from other creatures as human beings.

B. The metrics used in the research

self-efficacy scale: The researcher used the general self-efficacy scale that was developed by Eman Sahrayan, Muhammad, and Smaghavi 2015 for the purpose of determining the objectives of the research. to fit the research sample. Answer alternatives for the scale (0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 60%, 70%, 80%, 90%, 100%) Where do the scores correspond (0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10).

Social Intelligence Scale: The researcher used the Social Intelligence Scale (Silvera, Martinussen, & Dahl, 2001). In order to determine the objectives, set in the research, where the scale consists of 21 items. The answer alternatives for the scale (never,hardly ever, sometimes, often, very often) and that the scores agree (0, 1, 2, 3, 4)

C. Scientific bases used for the tests:

The tests are well done if the correct scientific bases are available (honesty, stability and objectivity) (Muhammad Jassim Al-Yasiri) After conducting the tests, the researcher found the scientific bases in the following form.

Content Verified :The test was presented to (14) experts from psychologists as well as sports psychologists. Table No. 1 also shows the value of the Chi-square. The experts' opinions for accepting or rejecting the self-efficacy measure. Their opinions were analyzed using the statistical law (Ca2).

Table (1): indicates the validity and validity of the self-efficacy questionnaire

No	Vertebrae	relative importance		Ca2	percentage	Importance level
		valid	Novalid			
A	1- 2- 3- 4- 5- 6- 7- 8- 9- 10- 11- 12- 13- 14- 15- 16- 17- 18- 19- 20	14	0	14	%100	Sig
B	21- 22	13	1	7,364	92,85 %	Sig

As for the social intelligence scale, Given to a group of experts (14). Table 2 Shows the degree of Chi square for experts' opinions for acceptance or rejection .The items of the scale were found to be suitable for adopting the social intelligence scale, and none of its items was dropped

Table (2) shows the validity of the social intelligence scale

No	Vertebrae	relative importance		Ca2	percentage	Importance level
		valid	No valid			
A	1- 2- 3- 4- 5- 6- 7- 8- 9- 10- 11- 12- 13- 14- 15- 16- 17- 18- 19- 20- 21	14	0	14	%100	Sig

III. METHOD OF TEST AND RETEST

In order to find out the evidence, the researcher used the method of testing and re-testing the self-efficacy and social intelligence. The test was applied to a group of 20 handball players on Saturday 25/12/2021 and the test was conducted again after 4 days for the same first group, and as shown in Table No. 3 and it was found that the tests were highly stable

Table (3) Method of Test and retest

No	Paragraphs	correlation	tabular value	Importance level
A	self-efficacy	0,99	0,19	Sig
B	social intelligence	0,97		

A. Initial experience

The researcher has conducted an exploratory experiment a group of 20 handball players on Saturday 25/12/2021 to test the self-efficacy and social intelligence test. The aim of this experiment is

- 1- Seeing the time of the player needs for the average answer on the self-efficacy scale, which amounted to 25 minutes
- 2- Seeing the time of player needs for the average answer on the social intelligencescale, which was 20 minutes
- 3- Knowing the obstacles that the researcher may face

B. Main experience

After he made sufficient reading to know the obstacles that may face the research, the researcher prepared all the requirements required for the research and with the help of an assistant work team, a sample of 60 handball players was tested in AL-Qadisiya Iraq. The researcher conducted the test for 15 days because the research sample are handball players in clubs, with the researcher's keenness not to interfere and giving the sample members sufficient time to answer the questionnaire.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tests were carried out on the sample by the researcher, and after the test, the data was processed by statistical means to achieve the objectives of the research, as those results were explained and analyzed in order to verify the hypotheses.

Table (4) means, standard deviation and correlation of the self-efficacy and social intelligence of handball players

No	Paragraphs	Mean	standard deviation	correlation	Importance level
A	self-efficacy	68,75	10,099	0,891	Sig
B	social intelligence	10,363	3,060		

Through the data that appeared in Table 4, it shows the difference in the degrees of self-efficacy and social intelligence of handball players. The result found shows a Correlation between search variables. The self-efficacy variable, the mean value was (68.75), the standard deviation value (10,099) and the Correlation ratio (0.891), and this ratio was found to be greater than tabular at the degree of freedom (42) and it indicates that correlation is large. As for the social intelligence variable, the mean was (10,363), standard deviation was (3,060), and the correlation was (0.891), It is greater than the scheduled. This indicates that the correlation is important and through the results it was found that There is a statistically significant relationship between self-efficacy and social intelligence. In the light of this study, it indicates that it is a good experience for the sport of handball, as it leads to the athlete's feeling of having a good self-efficacy that is useful in practicing the appropriate sport and making decisions at the appropriate time.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Self-efficacy and social intelligence are psychological factors have a vital role decision-making. The sense of belonging to the community is very important in order to reduce the rates of dropout and retention of judgments. The aim of the study was to know the self-efficacy and social intelligence of handball players in Al-Qadisiyah, Iraq. The researcher concluded that there are statistically significant differences between the average degrees of self-efficacy and the average degrees of social intelligence among handball players in Al-Qadisiyah Governorate, Iraq, where the correlation between the two variables was very high.

The researcher recommended the following recommendations:

- It is necessary to take care of athletes, solve their problems and develop self-efficacy to reach the positive side of their public life, especially in sports.
- The coaches should pay attention to the psychological aspects of the athletes, the social intelligence in order to advance the sports side to the best levels.
- Intensifying serious work on the media side in all forms (visual, read and audio) in order to enhance the self-efficacy and social intelligence of athletes in general and handball players in particular in order to find appropriate and sound solutions to meet the obstacles in sports and daily life.

REFERENCES

[1] Al-Haliq, M., Altahayneh, Z., and Oudat, M. (2014). Levels of burnout among sports referees in Jordan. *J. Phys. Educ. Sport* 14, 47–51.

[2] Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. New York: Freeman.

[3] Bandura, Albert (2010), "Self-Efficacy", *The Corsini Encyclopedia of Psychology*, American Cancer Society, pp. 1–3, doi:10.1002/9780470479216.corpsy0836, ISBN 978-0-470-47921-6, retrieved 2021-03-20.

[4] Cantor, N., Norem, J. K., Niedenthal, P. M., Langston, C. A., & Brower, A. M. (1987). Life tasks, self-concept ideals, and cognitive strategies in a life transition. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*. 53(6). Pp. 1178-1191

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- [5] Devine, D. J., Clayton, L. D., Philips, J. L., Dunford, B. B., and Melner, S. B. (1999). Teams in organizations prevalence, characteristics, and effectiveness. *Small Group Res.* 30, 678–711. doi: 10.1177/104649649903000602
- [6] Engel, D., Woolley, A. W., Jing, L. X., Chabris, C. F., and Malone, T. W. (2014). Reading the mind in the eyes or reading between the lines? Theory of mind predicts collective intelligence equally well online and face-to-face. *PLoS ONE* 9: e115212. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0115212
- [7] Engel, D., Woolley, A. W., Aggarwal, I., Chabris, C. F., Takahashi, M., Nemoto, K., et al. (2015). “Collective Intelligence in computer-mediated collaboration emerges in different contexts and cultures,” in *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI'15)* (New York, NY: ACM).
- [8] Guillén, F., and Feltz, D. L. (2011). A conceptual model of referee efficacy. *Front. Psychol.* 2:25. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2011.00025
- [9] Haney, C. J., and Long, B. C. (1995). Coping effectiveness: a path analysis of self-efficacy, control, coping, and performance in sport competitions. *J. Appl. Soc. Psychol.* 25, 1726–1746. doi: 10.1111/j.1559-1816.1995.tb01815.x
- [10] Helsen, W. F., Starkes, J. L., and Hodges, N. J. (1998). Team sports and the theory of deliberate practice. *J. Sport Exer. Psychol.* 20, 12–34. doi: 10.1123/jsep.20.1.12
- [11] Hinsz, V. B. (2015). Teams as technology: strengths, weaknesses, and trade-offs in cognitive task performance. *Team Perform. Manage.* 21, 218–230. doi: 10.1108/TPM-02-2015-0006.
- [12] Kihlstrom, J. F., & Cantor, N. (2000). Social intelligence. In R. J. Sternberg (Ed.), *Handbook of intelligence* .Pp : 359–379
- [13] Kellett, P., and Shilbury, D. (2007). Umpire participation: is abuse really the issue? *Sport Manag. Rev.* 10, 209–229. doi: 10.1016/S1441-3523(07)70012-8
- [14] Lewis, B. A., Williams, D. M., Frayeh, A., and Marcus, B. H. (2016). Self-efficacy versus perceived enjoyment as predictors of physical activity behaviour. *Psychol. Health* 31, 456–469. doi: 10.1080/08870446.2015.1111372
- [15] McMahon, C., Helsen, W. F., Starkes, J. L., and Weston, M. (2007). Decisionmaking skills and deliberate practice in elite association football referees. *J. Sports Sci.* 25, 65–78. doi: 10.1080/02640410600718640
- [16] Mohammed Jasim Al-Yasseri. *Theoretical foundations for the tests of sports education*. AlNajaf Al-Ashraf, 2010.
- [17] Nazarudin, M. N., Abdullah, M. R., Omar Fauzee, M. S., Abdullah, N. M., Noordin, H., and Suppiah, P. K. (2014). Psychological skills assessment and referee rugby sevens performance. *J. Educ. Thinkers* 5, 165–184.
- [18] Reeve, J., Cole, S. G., and Olson, B. C. (1986). Adding excitement to intrinsic motivation research. *J. Soc. Behav. Pers.* 1, 349–363.
- [19] Weinberg, R. S., and Richardson, P. A. (1990). *Psychology of Officiating*. Champaign, IL: Leisure Press.